

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP2 – Improving the collection, analysis and interpretation of pregnancy pharmacovigilance data

D2.1 Report on stakeholder workshop: “Moving pregnancy pharmacovigilance into the 21st century: pregnancy cohorts, registries and adverse event monitoring”

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Document History

Version	Date	Description
V0.1	02/03/2023	First draft
V0.2	06/04/2023	Second draft
V0.3	20/04/2023	Circulation for review by contributors
V1.0	23/05/2023	Submission to project management office
V1.1	13/06/2023	Final submission

Abstract/Executive Summary

This report summarises the key aspects and findings of the “**Moving pregnancy pharmacovigilance into the 21st century**” cross-stakeholder workshop, delivered on 25th January 2022 by IMI ConcePTION WP2, under task 2.1.

The objectives of the workshop were to:

- **Communicate current deficiencies and barriers** in existing pregnancy pharmacovigilance data collection systems
- Provide an **overview of the work** being undertaken **in WP2 to address these deficiencies**
- Bring key stakeholders together to **gain feedback** on the work of WP2 and how well it addresses stakeholder perceived barriers and deficiencies
- Gain cross-stakeholder insights to **inform sustainability models** and guidance on future approaches to pregnancy pharmacovigilance.

Members of Task 2.1 with the support of WP6 and WP5, planned and delivered a two-hour virtual workshop consisting of short presentations followed by structured audience interaction/feedback facilitated by polls, chat, and GroupMap. Four hundred and ninety-one people from 49 different countries, and representing a range of stakeholder groups, registered for the workshop.

Feedback from workshop participants provided overwhelming support for the projects ongoing within WP2. Participants provided particularly enthusiastic endorsement of long-term data collection in the LIFETIME study and highlighted the importance of stable infrastructure and funding to ensure sustainability of such a system. Additional qualitative analysis of stakeholder feedback is underway and is expected to be submitted to a journal as a Short Communication.

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List of abbreviations

CDE	Core Data Elements
EFPIA	European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations
EHR	Electronic Health Record
EMA	European Medicines Agency
ENTIS	European Network of Teratology Information Services
HIV	Human Immunodeficiency Virus
HCP	Healthcare Professional
IMI	Innovative Medicines Initiative
MS	Multiple Sclerosis
MHRA	Medicines and Healthcare Products Regulatory Agency
PRRC	Person Responsible for Regulatory Compliance
PV	Pharmacovigilance
QPPV	Qualified Person for Pharmacovigilance
WP	Work Package

Introduction

On 25 January 2022 11-13 CET, Task 2.1 members of Work Package 2 of the IMI ConcePTION project hosted an online stakeholder workshop “Moving pregnancy pharmacovigilance into the 21st century”. The full workshop presentation can be found here: [Moving pregnancy pharmacovigilance into the 21st century | Stakeholder workshop, 25 January 2022 - YouTube](#)

The aim of the workshop was to communicate current deficiencies and barriers in existing pregnancy pharmacovigilance primary data collection systems, provide an overview of the work being undertaken in WP2 to address these deficiencies, and to seek stakeholder feedback on both, to inform sustainability models and guidance on future approaches to pregnancy pharmacovigilance.

The content of the workshop was targeted at individuals with a personal or professional interest or experience in the collection and dissemination of data for the purpose of pregnancy pharmacovigilance or the treatment of pregnant women. There was also a focus on the inclusion of women who are or have been pregnant, and for whom this topic was of interest or importance.

Workshop participants

Following informal stakeholder grouping and analysis by Task 2.1 team members, a range of stakeholders (women, their partners, health care professionals, researchers, and representatives from companies that develop medicines and regulatory authorities) were invited to participate in the workshop through an invitation (Appendix 1) cascaded by IMI ConcePTION project members and the IMI ConcePTION Twitter account. In the light of the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic, a virtual format was deemed more feasible than an in-person workshop and created the opportunity to involve a much larger number of participants in the discussion

Four hundred and ninety-one people registered (Figure 1) from 49 different countries, with the largest number of participants joining from the United States, the United Kingdom and Poland (Figure 2). The most well-represented group was persons from pharma. Participants were asked to complete a series of pre-registration questions (Appendix 2). A maximum of 389 participants attended the workshop with well over 200 participants joining for the whole two-hour session.

Figure 2: Countries of residence of workshop participants. Legend shows number of participants registered per country.

Figure 1: Summary of the roles of workshop participants

Summary of the event's format

The workshop consisted of a two-hour long agenda (Appendix 3) delivered online via Zoom and hosted by ConcePTION partner, the Synergist. Following a welcome by the facilitator and a short introduction to the IMI ConcePTION project there was a series of 20-minute presentations by WP2 partners. Each presentation provided an overview of the tasks being undertaken in WP2, illustrating how the work will address a deficiency in the current system. Stakeholder interaction/feedback was invited after presentations in a structured fashion using interactive polls and the chat function in zoom. Verbal discussions were not feasible due to the large number of participants and therefore participants remained on mute for the duration of the workshop but were able to post comments in the chat.

Participants were also invited to provide further ideas and comments throughout the meeting using GroupMap (www.groupmap.com). GroupMap is an interactive tool designed for real-time brainstorming and discussion at virtual meetings. The tool allowed all participants, regardless of SH group, the opportunity to provide and respond to comments anonymously throughout the meeting, and for one week after the meeting to allow further input and comments, and to endorse or disagree with proposals put forward.

Presenters

- **Professor Dipak Kalra** (Facilitator)

Professor Kalra is the President of the European Institute for Innovation through Health Data and a retired Professor of Medical Informatics at University College London. He is a former UK General Practitioner and has 30 years of experience in European projects on electronic health records, interoperability, data protection and data reuse for research

- **Dr Dave Lewis**

Dr Lewis joined Novartis in 2007 following 20 years in pharmacovigilance at GSK and at Shire. He has been Head of the QPPV PRRC Office at Novartis in 2019. He has worked in country affiliates and in a variety of global safety & risk management functions with both investigational & marketed products, as well as in roles involving systems and processes. Dr Lewis is the author of over 30 papers on the safety of medicines and is an Honorary Senior Lecturer (Clinical) in the School of Life and Medical Sciences, University of Hertfordshire, UK. He is also a member of the ICH E2D(R1) Expert Working Group, and Work Package Co-Leader for IMI ConcePTION.

■ **Dr Laura Yates**

Dr Yates is the academic lead of Work Package 2 in the IMI ConcePTION Project and a Consultant Clinical Geneticist and Teratologist, based at the Newcastle-upon-Tyne Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust. Prior to her move to South Africa in 2018, she was Head of the UK Teratology Information Service (2009-2018) and is past President of the European Network of Teratology Information Services. Dr Yates has led and is involved in several international rare disease and teratology projects. She returned to the UK in 2021 following 3 years in South Africa developing genetic and teratology services in KwaZulu-Natal. Dr Yates previously chaired the Independence and Transparency Working Group and Pregnancy Special Interest Group of the EMA's, European Network of Centres for Pharmacoepidemiology and Pharmacovigilance (ENCePP), and was a member of the UK Northern Congenital Abnormality Survey (NorCAS) Steering committee. She sat on expert committees and Scientific Advisory Groups for the MHRA and EMA.

■ **Professor Eugène Puijtenbroek**

Professor Puijtenbroek is a medical doctor and clinical pharmacologist who has been working at the Netherlands Pharmacovigilance Centre Lareb since 1994. He is a professor of pharmacovigilance at the Faculty of Science and Engineering, Department of Pharmacotherapy, -Epidemiology and -Economics of the University of Groningen, the Netherlands. He has obtained a vast experience analysing signals in the spontaneous reporting system of the Netherlands and published in national as well as international journals. Next to his work in pharmacovigilance he has been working as a general practitioner from 1991 till 2006. His current field of attention is the development of signal detection methodologies, especially the integration of the statistical approach combined with the use of clinical information. He was a member of the Executive Board of the International Society of Pharmacovigilance from 2006 till 2012 and is currently member of the ISoP Scientific Board. He was co-opted member of the Pharmacovigilance Working Party of the European Medicines Agency from 2010 till 2012. He is a member of the editorial board of Drug Safety since 2001 and Chair of the Signal Management Review Technical Working Group.

■ **Dr Amalia Alexe**

Dr Alexe is policy & liaison lead at QPPV PRRC Office Novartis, Geneva and a PhD candidate at the University of Hertfordshire, UK.

■ **Dr Guillaume Favre**

Dr Favre graduated from MedSchool in Lyon, France and moved to Lausanne, Switzerland to achieve his Obstetrics and Gynecology residency. He started a PhD in perinatal epidemiology in 2020, and participated in the ConcePTION project 2.5.2 as a member of the Swiss Teratogen Information Service (STIS).

■ **Dr Rebecca Bromley**

Dr Bromley is Task 2.3 and Demo 3 lead within IMI ConcePTION. She is a Paediatric Neuropsychologist at the University of Manchester and Royal Manchester Children's Hospital. Her clinical and research interests surround exposure to medications in the womb and the possible impact on later child cognitive, motor and social development. Dr Bromley has consulted on pregnancy pharmacovigilance topics for the EMA and the UK MHRA and she collaborates with several different Expert by Experience Groups and UK epilepsy charities. In the NHS Dr Bromley works as part of Complex Epilepsy Team at Royal Manchester Children's Hospital and also the Manchester Rare Conditions Centre.

Workshop proceedings

Introduction and principles of engagement

The meeting chair and facilitator, Dipak Kalra, welcomed the participants, informing them that the meeting would be recorded and that comments in the chat would be saved and curated so that anonymized answers could be presented in the workshop report.

Dipak introduced the IMI ConcePTION principles of engagement before explaining the functionality of GroupMap. Maximillian Rauch (from Synergist), in collaboration with colleagues from the ConcePTION communications team, provided the secure link to the GroupMap in the zoom chat at the meeting start, and again at various intervals throughout the meeting to enable late comers to join. Participants were required to register with GroupMap in order to contribute or view the document.

Following the introduction to the event, presentation of the agenda, general housekeeping and an overview of Zoom etiquette, Dipak handed over to ConcePTION WP 2 leads, Dave Lewis and Laura Yates.

Presentation 1: ConcePTION's WP2: Collecting primary data on exposed pregnancies

Dave Lewis introduced the WP2 leadership team. Following a summary of the demographics of participants registered for the workshop, Dave gave an overview of the IMI ConcePTION project. He highlighted the multidisciplinary nature of the collaboration within the project, the project's funding (from European government and European pharmaceutical industry association (EFPIA)) and its overarching aim to improve public health across Europe. Dave gave a brief overview of the work packages within IMI ConcePTION which aim to provide definitions and statistical methods for collection and analysis of pregnancy exposure data, as well as improved communication methods for education and dissemination of information about medicine use in pregnancy and breastfeeding.

Dave presented the aims of WP2; to optimise primary data collection, sharing, and analysis. He introduced demonstration work in five main areas, undertaken with formal clinical protocols, to validate methods and approaches to pregnancy pharmacovigilance.

Watch Dave's full presentation here: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-8h6v47ycDg&list=PL28USx-3Tbr53aMwaKV5_YdQDHjPOKR-m&index=1

Presentation 2: Why ConcePTION WP2?

Laura Yates introduced the aims and scope of WP2 giving thalidomide, both a historically significant and modern-day teratogen, as an example of the importance of being able to quickly identify new teratogens, structural or neurodevelopmental, and the need to improve pregnancy pharmacovigilance systems.

Laura explained the many and varying primary data sources which were in scope for WP2, (with Electronic Healthcare Records (EHRs) being out of scope for the workshop and the focus of WP1) and the many barriers to efficient use of pregnancy data within those sources. She explained that WP2 aimed to improve the current situation by optimising the way in which we collect and analyse pregnancy exposure data.

Laura gave the example of dolutegravir (an antiviral used predominantly for the management of HIV infection) as an example of the importance of involvement of pregnant women in pregnancy pharmacovigilance and the risk-benefit discussion, and highlighted the ongoing need for prospective data collection.

Watch Laura's full presentation here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rou4zq8vasA>

Presentation 3: Results of data quality assessments from ConcePTION WP2 demonstration study 1

Eugène Puijenbroek highlighted the need to be informed about the nature and content of various sources of information on drug exposure during pregnancy. As an example, he mentioned some discrepancies which can be present when looking at patient compared to clinician reported outcomes. He presented a new tool developed in WP2 to measure clinical quality of pregnancy exposure reports. This new tool, called 'PregDoc' has been developed through a process of expert consultation and validated and tested on 160 real cases from various real-world primary data sources, held by WP2 member organisations.

Watch Eugène's full presentation here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ng67VswfuEg>

Stakeholder feedback on data quality assessments: key points (Full data is presented in Appendix 4A)

- Interactive poll questions indicated that the majority of participants (69%) **were not always sure of the trustworthiness of pregnancy data sources.**
- Participants overwhelmingly supported (97%) the **utility and usefulness** of a tool such as PregDoc in the assessment of quality of case reports.
- The majority of participants (69%) felt that pregnancy related information **should not be limited to predefined fields** but should be accompanied by the clinical narrative

Presentation 4: The ConcePTION data source catalogue

Amalia Alexe presented the ConcePTION data source catalogue, a resource which will be publicly available to search primary sources of pregnancy exposure data for different medicines (<https://conception.molgeniscloud.org/login>). Amalia gave an example of how one could search for primary data sources, for example for data on fingolimod exposure in pregnancy, how reports on organisations' data can be extracted, and how entries from the catalogue can be extracted into an Excel document, for further analysis of the scope of the data available in different sources.

Watch Amalia's full presentation here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=moIN9Zxi0v8>

Stakeholder feedback on data source catalogue: key points (Full data is presented in Appendix 4B)

- Results of the interactive poll showed that most participants thought it **should be a requirement that data sources are listed in a catalogue so that they are 'findable'**. There was 100% support from HCPs and parents, 79% of researchers, 73% of industry, and 67% of regulators. There was evidence of *some uncertainty* (those voting 'no' or 'don't know') from industry (27%), regulators (34%) and researchers (21%).
- Most participants thought the data catalogue would be **useful to them personally**. There was 100% support from parents and regulators, 97% of researchers, 90% of HCPs, and 89% of industry.
- There was overwhelming support for making the data catalogue **publicly available**. There was 100% support from HCPs and parents, 79% of researchers, 73% of industry, and 67% of regulators

Presentation 5. Optimizing analysis of existing cohort and registry data

In a video introduced by academic study lead Ursula Winterfield, Guillaume Favre introduced the methodology employed in WP2 demonstration study 2.5.2 to optimise the analysis of existing pregnancy exposure data and highlighted the difficulties of interpreting data from different sources which use different data collection systems and definitions.

Guillaume explained that key to optimising analysis of existing data was mapping it to a set of ‘core data elements’ (a clearly defined set of data elements with standardised definitions which should be collected in a pregnancy exposure report). Guillaume presented examples of items from the CDE developed in WP2- demonstrating the level of detail included in the definitions provided for each data element.

Guillaume introduced the 2.5.2 demonstration project, which will apply the CDE and aligned statistical methodology to data on pregnant women who took medications for Multiple Sclerosis (MS) from multiple sources.

Watch Guillaume’s full presentation here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XVBkLwQ5vOo>

Stakeholder feedback on CDE: key points (Full data is presented in Appendix 4C)

- Interactive polling showed strong support (94%) for a **standardised method** to analyse and compare data collected by different organisations.
- There was strong support for adoption of a single CDE and standardised analysis methods by organisations collecting data on pregnancy exposures.
- The majority of participants agreed that they would be **supportive of adopting the approach** presented (data transformed to CDE, standardised data analysis, collaboration with ConcePTION team for expertise) to compare pregnancy safety data collected
- A number of comments on GroupMap identified current **data deficiencies and barriers** which were relevant to the CDE:

“Data inconsistency”

“No harmonised collection of maternity data in healthcare systems”

“Variety of existing systems across EU”

Presentation 6. The LIFETIME System: Incorporating neurodevelopmental and long-term health follow-up into existing and a new surveillance system

Rebecca Bromley explained the importance of longer term follow up of children to determine if exposures in pregnancy may have an effect on child health and neurodevelopment. She highlighted that there are far fewer international systems looking at longer term outcomes than structural malformations which are evident at birth. She surmised that neglecting this area of pharmacovigilance has significant consequences- with babies potentially being exposed to medicines that have an effect on their long-term health and development and women not having enough information to allow them to use their medicines with confidence in pregnancy.

Rebecca acknowledged the difficulties with long term follow-up which needs significant expertise and financial

investment. She introduced the LIFETIME study as a solution. LIFETIME extends existing data collections and asks parents to complete a series of validated developmental questionnaires as a cost-effective approach, which will act as a surveillance system to flag medications at most need of urgent comprehensive investigation in order to assess risk.

Watch Rebecca's full presentation here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NWGslmFpjU8>

Stakeholder feedback on LIFETIME study: key points (Full data is presented in Appendix 4D and Appendix 5)

- In interactive polling and in the chat function, participants were **extremely supportive of LIFETIME**
- 92% of participants who voted felt that long-term follow-up should be **part of routine pregnancy PV**
- 50.3% (156/310) of participants felt that they would be more concerned about a **neurodevelopmental problem** than a **non-lethal structural birth defect**. 11.0% (34/310) were more concerned about a non-lethal structural birth defect while 38.7% (120/310) were 'not sure'.
- There was **overwhelming support** (85.8%) for the use of the LIFETIME system in pharmacovigilance, for screening of harmful neurodevelopmental effects of a medicine. Only 12.97% were not sure about this use of LIFETIME
- Comments in chat, and highly endorsed (via 'likes') comments on GroupMap, identified study of longer-term child outcomes as a **current deficiency** in data collection, and an area which could be improved.

“I want to understand the impact of my medication on my baby/child at birth but also as they grow up to become children and young adults. Sometimes problems are not always obvious at first. Especially if it's your first child, it's hard to know what to look for or what is unusual.”

“[It's] so important to follow up children longer term. As parents we want to know how what we take affects our children. Using existing infrastructure and learning also make sense.”
- Comments also highlighted the need for a long-term plan for sustainability and the need for guidance:

“Funding for digital systems are needed to create long-term follow up systems from birth and beyond.”

“Long term follow-up implies technical and governance stability of the designated collection system over decades, how to meet that challenge?”
- GroupMap also identified the need for **guidance on duration of follow-up** following delivery/birth

Presentation 7. TeratoPHEN –genetics & geneticists in pregnancy pharmacovigilance

Laura Yates highlighted the importance of genetic investigation in pregnancy pharmacovigilance and the interplay between genetics and medications. She introduced “TeratoPHEN” (from **Teratogen** and **Phenotype**), a platform being developed in collaboration with the Decipher team in Cambridge, UK, to support fuller delineation of teratogenic syndromes and detection of major teratogens.

Laura provided the example of Mycophenolate-induced Embryopathy as a phenocopy of the genetic condition CHARGE syndrome (derived from the common features of this genetic disorder: **Coloboma**, **Heart defects**, **Atresia choanae** (also known as choanal atresia), growth **Retardation**, **Genital abnormalities**, and **Ear abnormalities**) to illustrate the importance of ruling out genetic aetiology to prevent false associations being generated for medicines.

Laura explained that WP2 will work with the Decipher consortium (based in Cambridge, UK) to utilise and adapt the existing and well established Decipher platform (www.deciphergenomics.org), originally developed to support global efforts in deep phenotyping and genetic testing in rare disease diagnosis. The platform will be adapted to make it suitable for collecting information about drug exposure in pregnancy. The platform has a number of features which will be useful in deep phenotyping of patients with exposure to medicines in pregnancy including, in the future, the potential to explore use of computer analytics of facial photos to identify teratogenic syndromes or to create composite pictures which highlight common features. The platform also has a matchmaking feature which allows clinicians to query other clinicians on the platform if they have patients

exhibiting similar birth defects. The platform therefore has the potential to establish a global collaboration between clinicians, in particular clinical geneticists and quickly highlight potential associations. Laura introduced the planned pilot outline for WP2 demonstration study 4 using the Decipher system.

Watch Laura’s full presentation here: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RZFcKyqEPaI&list=PL28USx-3Tbr53aMwaKV5_YdQDHjPOKR-m&index=7

Stakeholder feedback on TeratoPHEN: key points (Full data is presented in Appendix 4E)

- The majority of participants who responded (87.3%, 137/157) agreed that access to **assessment by a geneticist and genetic testing** was important to a future pregnancy pharmacovigilance system
- Only a small proportion of participants (8.9%, 10/112) indicated that they would not want to **provide photos** for a medication safety assessment.
- The majority of parent stakeholders (80%, 4/5) indicated that they would prefer to provide photographs for assessment via a **face-to-face route**. HCP, industry, regulator and researchers indicated a preference for providing photographs via a **secure app or website** (30%, 29/98)
- The participants indicated that a detailed description of a teratogenic syndrome would be most useful when making decisions about using or prescribing a medicine in pregnancy (selected by 78.57% and 74.11% of those who expressed an opinion) and when making a decision about an unplanned pregnancy whilst on medication (selected by 66.07% of respondents).

Presentation 8: The ConcePTION App

Amalia Alexa introduced the ConcePTION app as a solution to increase the **volume** and **quality** of information available about medicines exposures during pregnancy and breastfeeding, and a way that parents and healthcare professionals can contribute to the data.

The first version of the app will be launched in UK, in English. The ConcePTION app is developed by redesigning IMI WEB-RADR PV app, which was developed through a collaboration between the WHO, UMC and the MHRA. The app will allow women and HCPs to report but it will also provide a newsfeed as a way of receiving trusted medicines information.

Watch Amalia’s full presentation here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=f5fJKYBPb-Y>

Stakeholder feedback on ConcePTION App: key points (Full data is presented in Appendix 4F)

- The majority of participants who voted indicated that factors which would motivate them to use a reporting app would be access to evidence-based information on medicines (100%), the wish to understand the risks and benefits of medicines (80%) and the wish to make informed decisions about taking medicines (71%).
- 38% of respondents indicated that they would be motivated to use an app to contribute to **decisions about personal health**
- A smaller number of participants were interested in **participation in clinical trials** using the app (25%), in the **adoption of new technologies** (21%) and in the **acknowledgement of personal contribution** (21%)
- Participants deemed that **ease of use, provision of trusted medical information** and **privacy and security** were the **most important factors** for an app.
- The **ability to use offline** and **intuitive use** were deemed the **less important factors** for the app.
- The **main concerns** regarding the app were **data security** and **lack of time for reporting**.
- Participants were less concerned about costs to use or transmit data, benefits of using an app and technological challenges.

GroupMap provided a number of insights relevant to the app:

A “**lack of accessible system for patients**” was identified as a barrier to pregnancy PV

Comments supported the idea that ease of use was an important factor for the app:

“Easy accessible and easy to understand tool (increase quality of direct reports from patients)”

“Good user experience- accessible for HCPs and pregnant women, fill in a form online, make it as streamlined a process as possible.”

Participants suggested that a data collection tool should be ***“Developed and validated by users, patients, pregnant females”*** with ***“Transparent data usage policies”***

GroupMap also highlighted the need for normal outcomes and unexposed pregnancies to be collected:

“Scarce information about the number of exposed pregnancies in post-marketing setting (i.e. lack of a reliable denominator)”

“Adequate comparator data and lack of information on background rates of adverse pregnancy outcomes in certain settings”

“Data on natural history of disease”

Groupmap Highlights

GroupMap provided opportunity for participants brainstorm together and give feedback in a less structured fashion than the electronic polls. Headings were provided to stimulate thoughts and to organise comments.

Highly endorsed comments on GroupMap

The comments which received the highest level of endorsement from other workshop participants (via 'likes') are presented below.

What are gaps and deficiencies in the current system?

Study of longer-term child outcomes following exposure (medicine) is often overlooked, despite lifelong consequences 17

Limited regulatory guidance 11 "There is limited guidance on outcomes other than birth defects", "Agree: harmonized approach across countries missing"

Scarce information about the number of exposed pregnancies in post-marketing setting (i.e. lack of a reliable denominator) 5

Information on 'normal' pregnancies with medication use 4

How do you think pregnancy pharmacovigilance can be IMPROVED?

Standardised data collections 28 "This would make it so much easier for so many reasons. Also information from my fellow women in Europe would give me confidence. It's a larger pool of women (not just national data) and the women (and health systems) have a similar profile. So we are comparing ourselves and our information (e.g comparing apples with apples instead of comparing apples and pears)".

Data should be collected more long term 17 further comment: "I want to understand the impact of my medication on my baby/child at birth but also as they grow up to become children and young adults. Sometimes problems are not always obvious at first. Especially if it's your first child, it's hard to know what to look for or what is unusual."

Guidance on duration of follow-up following delivery/birth 8

Lack of collection of data on fetal outcomes apart from teratology, for example fetal growth rate & wellbeing, placental function 7

What BARRIERS need to be addressed to implement improvements to pregnancy PV in the future?

Regulators need to drive drug development in pregnancy by using creative incentives and tools (akin to rare disease and PIP) 10

comment: further comment "I think that this would be preferable but i am not sure on the uptake of this, i.e. how many women would be willing to undergo this and take an uncertain risk to their unborn child. Would it be possible to assess the risks another way without using pregnant women?"

Funding is a barrier 7

Lack of linkage of PV databases 7

Variety of existing systems cross EU/ lack of systems 5

That is essential for you to TRUST a pregnancy pharmacovigilance system (report to or rely on information from)?

Transparency of data sources & analytical methods -> allow validation by independent researchers 11

Collaboration with pharma 10 "Collaboration is a hugely generic term. Involvement of pharma is important so that efforts are coordinated, however this requires impartiality. Independence of influence from pharma, which serves to be benefit financially, is vital for the trustworthiness of the data produced. This is a cornerstone of good scientific practice."

Independence from pharma 8 "I do feel that the Pharma industry's reputation should be reconsidered and there is a lot of misunderstanding out there on how the pharma industry operate when in fact it is a highly regulated environment governed by a strong set of principles. Past negative press regarding the pharmaceutical industry is not helpful and could possibly hamper any future progress where independence is sought."

"I think there would be more trust if there was independence from Pharma. A charity or something with a social purpose. It's hard to trust Pharma. Even though they have done a lot of good (eg COVID vaccine etc) you can't help viewing them a bit like tobacco companies."

Consistency in the way the data are collected and processed 6

Developed and validated by users, patients, pregnant females 6

Other thoughts and ideas

Get into national programmes e.g. handheld pregnancy notes for women should contain links for self reporting 9 further comment: "an all in one app for pregnant women/young families"

Include information on the importance of PV reporting in pregnancy tests further comment: "yes this would be really good option. Similar to the PIL inside medicine boxes advising on reporting to MHRA if any side effects are experienced."

Patient education 7

Educate teenagers, adolescents, young (future) mothers on PV and what is in for them (education programs at schools, universities...) 7

Notable GroupMap comments on breastmilk and medication use data

“As a parent no one could give me an answer on whether my medication was safe when breastfeeding. No professional knew anything. They just tell you it’s your choice. The burden is on us as parents (and potentially the consequences!). We are travelling blind here. I looked at all the medication leaflets, all types of official guidance, from health regulators to Pharma info. I literally searched everywhere and was left exasperated. In the end I took the risk and breastfed but it was so so stressful. It shouldn’t be like that. It should be a good time to feed your lovely new baby, as difficult as it can be sometimes, you are doing something wonderful and in theory breastfeeding is providing what the baby needs. Thinking you could be poisoning your baby without knowing just makes you want to cry.”

“Breastfeeding exposure reporting is not standardised, only if baby develops an AE as a result of breastfeeding may it be reported. Not enough awareness that breastfeeding and medicine usage in mother should ideally be captured and monitored accordingly.”

Notable GroupMap comments on maternity data collection in healthcare systems

“Data is possibly only reported if there is a issue with the baby and the physician assesses the link to be causally related, however, without proper case assessment using other sources of information, there could be other cases of malformation in the foetus which is causally related and this data has been overlooked due to a lack of a standardised approach to capturing data in this type of setting.”

Notable GroupMap comments regarding leadership of pregnancy pharmacovigilance

“Leadership: who is driving and sorting this out for each country? Often unclear or muddled”

“Yes, often different agencies or organisations think it’s someone else’s problem to deal with so in the end no one does anything”

Key themes summary

Stakeholder wants/needs	Work undertaken by IMI ConcePTION to address	Main barriers/challenges
Clear leadership with regards to pregnancy pharmacovigilance	Production of pregnancy PV guidelines for primary data collection, analysis and communication. Contribution to European and international guidance National initiatives based on systems developed within Conception WP and lead by WP2 members being piloted	Multi stakeholder engagement and consensus on pregnancy pharmacovigilance required Leadership on the European and national levels is required to drive adoption of recommendations
Long-term data collection for neurodevelopmental/child outcomes	WP2: LIFETIME project WP2	Stable technical solution and funding is required Development of clinical networks beyond epilepsy International implementation will be necessary
Guidance on how to include pregnant women in clinical trials	WP2 involved in shaping and providing input into international IHG Guidance on Pregnant Women in Clinical trials	Low number of pregnant women agreeing to participate Continuation of pregnant women in randomized trials when poor symptom control
Data on how pharmacokinetics of drugs change over the course of pregnancy	Outside current aims and scope of ConcePTION Systems and networks being developed	Requires active participation of pregnant women and significant investment in studies of this nature.
Better guidance on pregnancy data collection and length/nature of follow-up	Core data elements WP2 published and included in appendix if GVP III Guidance will be produced in Y5 of the project, informed by findings of demonstration studies and expert working group input	Adoption of CDE (barriers to this will be different depending on organisation)
Harmonised data collection, data consistency, complete data, less data		

fragmentation, data gathered with common objectives, no duplication of data		
Comparator data (background rates of outcomes in different settings)	WP1: Electronic healthcare records WP2: Systems and methodologies for Collection of data on all exposed pregnancies' including 'normal' outcomes	Requires widespread prospective data collection for all pregnancies and adoption of ConcePTION recommendations.
Information on all pregnancies including those with normal outcomes		
Data on natural history of disease		
Studies using data from current databases to highlight deficiencies and improvements	WP2: Demonstration projects	Clear plan to integrate learnings from demo projects into future data collections/studies
Data collection system which is accessible for patients	ConcePTION App & Teratophen Platform	Funding for roll out of app and for development of prospective data collection arm Establishing collaboration between established data collections and app to prevent data duplication Accessibility- user experience is important and therefore testing phase is important before roll-out
System developed and validated by users		
Evidence and information on the safety of medicines for breastfeeding	WP4 <u>generating evidence</u> animal models and milk biobank WP5 <u>Providing information</u> Signposting within Knowledge Bank to trustworthy resources	Continued support for studies using animal model and for maintenance of biobank. Funding to support Knowledge Bank
Patient education	WP5 Knowledge bank to use push-pull strategies to increase reporting 5.3 Raising awareness among the general public of importance of pregnancy PV- communications toolkit	Funding to support Knowledge Bank Strategy to direct women to the most appropriate place for reporting
Collaboration with midwives and pharmacists	WP2 Midwives to trial ConcePTION app in UK using test cases WP5 Educational course for HCPs to include information on reporting exposures	ConcePTION App and education package requires adoption by healthcare systems
Preconception/antenatal specialists should be available to review medicines before/early in pregnancy	Outside current scope of ConcePTION	Teratology information services are not available in every country Different countries may have varying levels of access to specialist training in teratology and risk communication. Information on medicines in pregnancy is not available in all languages to support counselling.

Discussion

Stakeholder needs and priorities

The virtual stakeholder meeting provided an effective method of collecting feedback from a large and diverse group of stakeholders. The following key messages are drawn from feedback obtained throughout the meeting:

- We were pleased to observe that many of the barriers and deficiencies identified by participants in the GroupMap brain storming exercise are those which we also believe are key issues for pregnancy pharmacovigilance. It was therefore reassuring, but unsurprising, that there was generally a high level of support for the work being undertaken in WP2.
- There was strong endorsement for PregDoc as a tool to assess the quality of case reports with most participants agreeing that they do not always know the quality of data sources.
- Most participants agreed that data should be findable and felt that the data catalogue would be useful to them. Importantly, participants felt that the data catalogue should be publicly available and this will be a key consideration for sustainability.
- Lack of data harmonisation and lack of linkage of diverse data collection systems were seen as major barriers to pregnancy PV. The participants endorsed the adoption of a single set of core data elements and standardised analysis.
- There was a general recognition that collection of long-term child neurodevelopment outcomes is a neglected and important area of PV. Indeed, over 50% of those who expressed an opinion in the polls felt that they would be more concerned about a neurodevelopmental problem than a non-lethal structural birth defect. There was particularly enthusiastic participation in feedback regarding the LIFETIME system. Feedback highlighted the need for funding to be available for stable infrastructure long-term (in terms of both governance and a technical solution).
- Participants provided valuable feedback for methodological considerations for the TeratoPHEN study. The small number of parents who attended the workshop indicated that they would mainly prefer to provide photographs for assessment via a face-face route whilst other participants indicated a preference for an online route. It could therefore be envisaged that a patient would be more likely to wish to participate in the study via their HCP, however, given the small number of parents that participated in the workshop, further stakeholder engagement is required to optimise recruitment strategy. Reassuringly, only a small proportion of participants indicated that they would not want to provide the photos that the assessment relies on.
- Feedback regarding the ConcePTION app highlighted the importance of ease of use and data security/privacy. Comments in GroupMap alluded to the fact that there are conflicting views about the role of pharma in data collection, with some participants suggesting that independence from pharma was an important trust marker, however others felt that collaboration with pharma was important. Given the high proportion of participants from a pharma background, this is an aspect which warrants further stakeholder input.
- All the participants who expressed an opinion felt that receiving evidence-based information would be the biggest motivator to use the ConcePTION app. This suggests the importance of collaboration with information dissemination tasks within WP5 of ConcePTION and potentially existing information resources available from ENTIS partners.
- Participants recognised the importance of establishing the denominator in the post-marketing setting and the need to collect data on 'normal' exposed pregnancies. This is an important consideration for future data collection and the development of prospective data collections.
- Participants felt that there was a particular dearth of evidence and information on the safety of medicines in breastfeeding and parents felt particularly alone in making decisions in respect to this.
- Comments reflected a general opinion that pregnancy pharmacovigilance is currently ineffective, with no organisation with clear responsibility for collection of data within countries, limited regulatory guidance and underinvestment.
- There were a number of excellent suggestions of how women could be made aware of pregnancy pharmacovigilance at the very start of their pregnancy by including information on reporting in pregnancy tests or by targeting national programmes, such as the handheld maternity notes used in some countries. Others suggested an even earlier approach by targeting education programmes in schools and universities.

Next steps

The workshop has provided important endorsement for the work undertaken in WP2 and for sustainability purposes, provides clear evidence that the work addresses a number of perceived barriers to effective pregnancy PV. Work going forward should continue to involve and to incorporate feedback from stakeholders and provide a clear plan to engage relevant stakeholders to ensure adoption of developed guidelines and methodologies after ConcePTION. A robust and timely funding and sustainability strategy is needed as a priority to ensure that progress made by WP2 to address the significant deficits in the current pregnancy PV system is not lost. Additional qualitative analysis of stakeholder feedback is underway and is expected to be submitted to a journal as a Short Communication.

Stakeholder feedback after the workshop

“Fantastic and very informative meeting. Looking forward to collaborating with people on this topic”

“Great workshop IMI ConcePTION!”

Acknowledgements

Many thanks to all attendees for their valuable input.

Appendix 1 Workshop promotion

IMI ConcePTION website

Workshop: Moving pregnancy pharmacovigilance into the 21st century: pregnancy cohorts, registries & safety monitoring

On 25 January 2022, the IMI ConcePTION project is organising an online workshop on improving how we collect information to understand the risk*Ns and benefits of medicine use in pregnancy and breastfeeding. We invite women, their partners, health care professionals, researchers and representatives from companies that develop medicines and authorities that approve them to join us. Your input will help us fill some of the knowledge gaps on the safety of medicines in pregnancy and breastfeeding, and help us to understand where there are barriers and problems with the existing systems!

Despite widespread initiatives to collect information on the safety of medicines in pregnancy & breastfeeding, the evidence is still either lacking or incomplete. To improve pregnancy pharmacovigilance and ensure that health care professionals and the women themselves have access to trustworthy,

updated and accurate information, we need to understand what barriers they face and work to fill gaps in the existing systems. But to succeed in developing a sustainable system for pharmacovigilance in pregnancy, we need input from the women who use medicines, the health care professionals that prescribe them, the companies that manufacture them, and the regulators that approve them.

As part of our efforts to collect better information on medication use during pregnancy and breastfeeding, the ConcePTION project will conduct a multi-stakeholder workshop. We need your feedback on our proposals!

This is an open online event. To join us on 25 January between 11-13 CET, we need you to register. The event is free of charge. The event is open to all stakeholder groups and organised so that anyone can contribute, regardless of how much you know about the topic beforehand. We are particularly interested in hearing from women who have used medicines during pregnancy, and health care professionals. Presentations will be recorded, and a report will be published on the ConcePTION website.

The workshop will address:

- Findings from the ConcePTION project which illustrate why the systems for collecting information on medicines use in pregnancy and breastfeeding need to be improved
- The ConcePTION project approach
- Our proposal for a pregnancy and breastfeeding pharmacovigilance system for the future!

[Register to join the workshop >>](#)

Appendix 2 Pre-registration questions

Q1. Which country/region are you joining from?

Q2. What organisation are you associated with?

Q3. I am joining this event primarily as a

- Health care professional
- Parent
- Person working in pharmaceutical industry
- Regulator
- Researcher
- Other

Q4. I am interested in receiving newsletters from ConcePTION

- Yes, please
- No, thank you

Q5. I agree to ConcePTION processing my data for the purposes on conducting this event

- I agree
- I don't want to register

Appendix 3 Stakeholder Workshop agenda

Time (CET)	Topic	Speakers
11.00 hrs	Introduction & principles for engagement	Dipak Kalra
	IMI ConCePTION and post-marketing safety data	Dave Lewis, Laura Yates
	Study 1 Data quality assessment	Yrea Weetink, Eugène van Puijenbroek
11.30 hrs	ConCePTION data catalogue	Amalia Alexe
	Study 2 Optimizing analyses of registry data	Guillaume Favre
	Study 3 The LifeTIME system for long-term health	Rebecca Bromley
	Study 4 TeratoPHEN – genetics and geneticists	Laura Yates
12.20 hrs	ConCePTION app for information and reporting	Amalia Alexe
	Q&A with panel discussion and summary	Dipak Kalra, Laura Yates
13.00 hrs	Close of meeting	

N.B panel discussion was not possible due to lack of time but questions were recorded and answered within the scope of this report. Discussion also took place within chat and on GroupMap.

Appendix 4 Poll results

A) Polls relating to Study 1 data quality assessment

B) Polls relating to the ConcePTION data catalogue

Do you think all data collectors should be required to register their data collection in a designated catalogue such as the ConcePTION data source catalogue to ensure that data are FINDABLE?

Would having updated information on pregnancy data collections in the ConcePTION catalogue be useful to you?

C) Polls relating to Study 2 Optimising analysis of registry data

Do you think that using a standardised method to analyse and compare data collected by different organisations may increase confidence in the results provided?

Should all organisations collecting data on medication use in pregnancy be required to use a standardised method of data collection and analysis?

If you needed to compare pregnancy safety data collected by different groups using different methods, would you support using the approach presented (data transformed to CDE, standardised data analysis)?

D) Polls relating to Study 3 The LIFETIME system

Do you think long term follow-up should be part of routine pregnancy pharmacovigilance?

Would you be more concerned about a medication causing a neurodevelopmental problem (e.g. autism, learning difficulties) or a non-lethal structural defect (e.g. hole in the heart, cleft palate)?

E) Polls relating to Study 4 TeratoPHEN and geneticists

Do you agree that access to assessment by a geneticist and genetic testing (if indicated) is important in a future pregnancy pharmacovigilance system?

Through which of the following routes would you be prepared to provide photographs of your child for the purpose of medication safety assessment (please select all that apply)?

When would having a more detailed description about a teratogenic syndrome be useful or important?

The most popular answers are presented.

F) Polls relating to the ConcePTION app

Appendix 5 Chat highlights

Question: Are there any proposed incentives for the parents to complete the questionnaires for up to 7+ years as this could potentially see a drop out percentage due to time and other commitments and this could have an effect on the accuracy of the data collected. Are there any perimeters being put in place to ensure that full data collection is obtained for the period specified?

Question: Can data from the LIFETIME study be used for other research purposes, in addition to pharmacovigilance for drugs used during pregnancy (with consent)? To make the best use of the time of the mothers, children and HCPs involved.

Answer (Rebecca Bromley): We agree that following up over the longer time takes a lot of commitment (researchers and families). We have done this in a few studies over the years. For LIFETIME this is one thing we are piloting, how we do this well, how we keep families engaged and what our loss to follow up rates are).

Comment: Thanks Rebecca. So important to follow up children longer term. As parents we want to know how what we take affects our children. Using existing infrastructure and learning also make sense.

Question: Long term follow-up implies technical and governance stability of the designated collection system over decades, how to meet that challenge?

Answer (Rebecca Bromley): Yes, technical and governance stability of the data collection is important. Funding is also critical over the longer time to ensure the system remains in place over the duration of the required follow up.

Comment: I think that's why we are here to solve those challenges